

FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT AND GROWTH OF RETAIL SECTOR IN INDIA

DR. HIMANSHU AGARWAL¹

INTRODUCTION

Retailing is defined as all activities involved in selling goods or services directly to final consumers for their personal, non-business use *via* shops, markets, door-to-door selling, mail order or over the internet, where the buyer intends to consume the product through personal, family or household dues. The retail sector of Indian economy is categorized into two segments as organized retail sector and unorganized retail sector with the latter holding the larger share of the retail market. At present, the organized retail sector is catching up very fast. It has encouraged large private sector players to invest in this sector. The impact of the alterations in the format of the retail sector changed the lifestyle of the Indian consumers drastically. As customers' taste and preferences are changing, the market scenario is also changing from time to time. With the onset of a globalized economy in India, the Indian consumer's psyche has been changed. Many foreign players have also entered India through different routes *such as* test marketing, franchising, and wholesale cash-and-carry operation.

Therefore, today's market scenario is very different from that of the market scenario before economic reforms of 1991 and there have been many factors responsible for the changing market scenario. Income level of the people has changed; life styles and social class of people have completely changed now than that of olden days. These changes have decreased the dependency of consumers on traditional method of purchasing. Today, we can see a new era in market with the opening up of many departmental stores, hypermarket, shopper's stop, malls, branded retail outlets and specialty stores.

Post liberalization, the Retail sector in India is heralded as one of the sunrise industries. It has never been better for the retail sector in India. Today within the booming service sector, retailing is the single biggest contributor in terms of GDP to the National Income.

a) Organized Retailing: Any retail outlet chain (and not a one shop outlet) which is professionally managed (even if it is family run), has accounting transparency (with proper usages of MIS and accounting standards) and organized supply chain management with centralized quality control and sourcing (certain part of the sourcing can be locally made) can be termed as an organized retailing in India. Organized retailing refers to trading activities undertaken by licensed retailers, that is, those who are registered for sales tax, income tax *etc.* These include the corporate-backed hypermarkets and retail chains and also the privately owned large retail businesses. Indian corporate *like* Reliance, ITC and Pantaloons have made foray into this segment along with several foreign brands changing the landscape of retailing in India. The growth in the organized retailing has resulted in the establishment of departmental stores, supermarkets, rural retailing, e-retailing and luxury retailing.

E-retail: The e-retail segment in India has enormous potential and is expected to grow from \$ 0.6 billion in 2012 to approximately \$ 76 billion by 2021, accounting for almost 5 percent of the Indian retail Industry, according to a study by Technopak.

Online retail has witnessed the sudden growth in India because of the various advantages it offers to the consumer such as ease of access, ability to compare product quality and prices, the wide product portfolio offered as well as the attractive prices and heavy discounts offered by major e-retail companies. The traders have also significant advantages such as, low capital requirement, easiness in choosing distribution channels.

Indian E-retail market is yet in the nascent stage with very few internet shoppers and with customer preferences not very favourable to e-shopping phenomenon. With the challenges abound, only the innovation of services and growth of internet users will define the success of e-retail shops.

¹ Associate Professor, Faculty of Commerce and Business Administration, D. N. (PG) College, Meerut

b) **Unorganized Retailing:** Any retail outlet which is run locally by the owner or the caretaker of the shop. Such outlets lack technical and accounting standardization. The supply chain and the sourcing are also done locally to meet the local needs. Unorganized retailing refers to the traditional formats of low - cost retailing, like the local *kirana* shops, owner manned general stores, *paan/beedi* shops, convenience stores, hand cart and pavement vendors etc. The unorganized retail sector is still dominant in India, since it has the advantage of low investment need. Unorganized retailers play an important role in this regard and are a vital part of the supply chain. If unorganized retail segment positions itself correctly, it can carve a niche for itself in India's booming retail sector.

Table 1: FDI Share of organized sector in selected countries

Country	Share of organized Sector (%)
U. S. A.	85
U. K.	80
Japan	66
Russia	36
India	04

(Source: Planel Retail & Technopak Adviser Pvt. Ltd.)

Fig.2: FDI Share of Organised Sector in Selected Countries

Source: Panel Retail & Technopak Adviser Pvt. Ltd.

Table 2: Projected Size of the Organized Retail Industry

Year	Increase in size (in crores)
2008	965
2010	1728
2015	5610
2022	17368

(Source: www.nsdcindia.org/pdf/organised-retail.pdf)

Fig. 3: Projected Organised Retail Industry

Source: www.nsdcindia.org/pdf/organised-retail.pdf

Presently, India is having the largest young population in the world and about 54 per cent of India's population is below 25 years of age and about 80 per cent are below 45 years (including this 54 per cent). The low medium age of population means a higher current consumption rate which is very suitable for the retail segment. Sizable disposable income in India is concentrated in the urban areas. A study reveals that 20 million middle class home rural India equal the number in urban India and hence purchasing power. Hence, there is a significant and considerable opportunity for organized retailers in the rural area.

The present research paper investigates the link between Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and Growth of Retail Sector in India because India presents a grand opportunities to the world at large, to use it as a business hub. Lots of studies are required to formulate policies for the retailers to capture the retail market segment, which is going to be very strong in the year to come.

1. Objectives of the Research

The specific objectives of the research paper, which are based on the need, importance and scope of the paper, are as under:

- i. To analyze the status and growth of retail sector in India.
- ii. To review the present literature on the FDI in retail sector in India.
- iii. To evaluate the impact of Foreign Direct Investment on various important sectors of Indian Economy.

2. Methodology

The study is conducted on all India level on the basis of secondary data. Secondary data is an important source of data on which this work is based. The author has collected the secondary data from various published and unpublished sources. The secondary data is also analyzed and used for drawing conclusion. The author used following sources for collection of secondary data:

- Reports and Publications of National and International Institutes.
- Reports of Government and NGOs.
- Various Research Journals, Periodicals and Newspapers.
- Internet Browsing.

3. Hypothesis

The hypothesis of the proposed research work is as follows:

- a. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has a positive impact on retail sector in India.
- b. There is an increase in the purchasing power of the Indian middle classes and the heavy influx of FDI in the retail sectors in India.
- c. There is positive correlation between growth of retail sector and Indian economy.
- d. Organized Retail Industry created an ample job opportunities in India.

4. Review Of Literature

The comprehensive literature centered on economies pertaining to empirical findings and theoretical rationale tends to demonstrate that FDI is necessary for sustained economic growth and development of any economy in this era of globalization. The reviewed literature is as follows:

Khare, Dr. Manish(2013) (*AISECT Journal Vol. II/ Issue IV Sep. 2013*) in his article "Foreign Direct Investment in Retail Sector – A SWOT Analysis" wrote that India's retail sector has undergone a rapid transformation over the past decade and this process is expected to strengthen in coming years with the rise in population, per capita income and urbanization. The Paper traces the economic progress made by India's Retail Sector in the planning era, and the emerging issues under globalization. It examines the socio-economic magnitudes, problems and challenges of the country as well as the pitfalls in FDI Planning in India. The paper also makes some policy suggestions to address the constraints in promoting sustainable FDI in India.

Nath, Dr. Hiranya K.(2013) (*Space and Culture.in /index.php/ space and culture/ article/view/17/7*) in his article "Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in India's Retail Sector" presented an overview of retail trade in India in the wake of the country's new policy that will allow foreign capital in multi-brand retailing. It discusses various potential benefits and costs of FDI in the retail sector, particularly in terms of its effects on traditional retailers, employment, consumers, farmers and local manufacturers. It argues that given somewhat slower growth projection for the Indian economy during the next decade, various structural issues including inadequate infrastructure and a lack of affordable real estate, and the prevalent structure of the agricultural markets, it is unlikely that all the potential benefits and costs will be realized to their fullest extent, at least in the foreseeable future. The economic dynamics and the political process will play an important role in determining the outcomes of this move to allow FDI in the retail sector and will ultimately determine the effects on various stakeholders.

Sikarwar, Deepshikha (2013) (*ET, 30 May, 2013, New Delhi*) opined in his short report "51% FDI in multi brand retail likely to include FII's" that Foreign retailers that want to set up retail stores in India have to mandatorily invest at least 50% of the total FDI brought in has to be invested in 'backend infrastructure' within three years of the first tranche of FDI wherein back-end infrastructure includes capital expenditure on agriculture market produce infrastructure and others. At least, \$ 100 million FDI has to be brought in by the foreign investors.

Agarwal, Dr. Himanshu (9-11 November, 2012) in his research paper "Impact of Foreign Direct Investment in Retail Sector in India" presented in 65th All India Commerce Conference of Indian Commerce Association wrote that the impact of the alterations in the format of the retail sector changed the lifestyle of the Indian

consumers drastically. As customers taste and preferences are changing, the market scenario is also changing from time to time. With the onset of a globalized economy in India, the Indian consumer's psyche has been changed. People have become aware of the value of money. Nowadays the Indian consumers are well versed with the concepts about quality of products and services. Consumer dynamics in India are changing and the retailers need to take note of this and formulate their strategies and tactics to deliver value to the consumer. Post liberalization, the Retail sector in India is heralded as one of the sunrise industries. It has never been better for the retail sector in India. Today within the booming service sector, retailing is the single biggest contributor in terms of GDP to the National Income. Foreign Direct Investment means an investment in a foreign country through the acquisition of a local company or the establishment there of an operation on a new site.

Pant, Manoj (2011) (ET: Dec. 9, Page14) in his article, "Who's Scared of Retail FDI" writes, "The debate on FDI in retail should start from first principles about the nature of FDI. The biggest gain from allowing FDI in retail would be to increase competition. The 51 per cent cap on multi-brand retail will only help entrenched players."

Joshi, Sharad (2011) (ET: Dec. 2, Page 10) concludes in his study "FDI in Retail is First Major Step towards Reforms in Agriculture" that FDI will help the farm sector set up the much needed backward linkage. Today, the existing organized retail has not been able to supply fresh vegetables to consumers because they have not invested in the backward linkages. The concern that the Indian farmer is illiterate and hence more prone to exploitation is not correct. Today, Indian farmer is heavily indebted. The cost of labour, electricity, diesel etc is all very high. The government does not give good price to his produce. Land is being fragmented. Our food security may come into danger if the farmer's financial health does not improve."

Dhoot, Venugopal, chairman and MD, Videocon group owner of NEXT with more than 600 stores, says that "Foreign investment may not be bread and butter, but it would have allowed us to expand at a faster pace and accelerate sales by providing much better deals to consumers."

Biyani, Kishore, CEO, Future Group reported that "We were growing at 25-30 per cent, but expected foreign investment will increase the growth rate to 40-50 per cent. Currently, we are working hard on cash flows for generating investment. FDI would have provided a fresh lease of life".

Balasubramanyam V.N Sapsford David (2007) in their article "Does India need a lot more FDI" compares the levels of FDI inflows in India and China, and found that FDI in India is one tenth of that of china. The paper also finds that India may not require increased FDI because of the structure and composition of India's manufacturing, service sectors and her endowments of human capital. The requirements of managerial and organizational skills of these industries are much lower than that of labour intensive industries such as those in China. Also, India has a large pool of well – Trained engineers and scientists capable of adapting and restructuring imported know – how to suit local factor and product market condition all of these factors promote effective spillovers of technology and know- how from foreign firms to locally own firms. The optimum level of FDI, which generates substantial spillovers, enhances learning on the job, and contributes to the growth of productivity, is likely to be much lower in India than in other developing countries including China. The country may need much larger volumes of FDI than it currently attracts if it were to attain growth rates in excess of 10 per cent per annum. Finally, they conclude that the country is now in a position to unbundle the FDI package effectively and rely on sources other than FDI for its requirements of capital.

Crespo Nuno and Fontoura Paula Maria (2007) in their paper "Determinant Factors of FDI Spillovers – What Do We Really Know?" analyze the factors determining the existence, dimensions and sign of FDI spillovers. They identify that FDI spillovers depend on many factors like absorptive capacities of domestic firms and regions, the technological gap, or the export capacity.

Lisa De Propis and Nigel Driffield (2006) in their study "The Importance of Cluster for Spillovers from Foreign Direct Investment and Technology Sourcing", examine the link between cluster development and

inward foreign direct investment. They concluded that firms in clusters gain significantly from FDI in their region, both within the industry of the domestic firm and across other industries in the region.

Miguel D. Ramirez (2006) in his study "Is Foreign Direct Investment Beneficial for Mexico: An Empirical Analysis" examines the impact of Foreign Direct Investment on labour productivity function for the 1960- 2001 period is estimated that includes the impact of changes in the stock of private and foreign capital per worker. The error correction model estimates suggest that increase in both private and foreign investment per worker have a positive and economically significant effect on the rate of labour productivity growth. However, after taking into account the growing remittances of profits and dividends, there is a marked decrease in the economic effect of foreign capital per worker on the rate of labour productivity growth. The study assesses the short – term interactions of the relevant variables via impulse response functions and variance decompositions based on a decomposition process that does not depend on the ordering of the variables.

Nirupam Bajpai and Jeffrey D. Sachs (2006) in their paper "Foreign Direct Investment in India: Issues and Problems", attempted to identify the issues and problems associated with India's current FDI regimes, and more importantly the other associated factors responsible for India's unattractiveness as an investment location. Despite India offering a large domestic market, rule of law, low labour costs, and a well working democracy, her performance in attracting FDI flows have been far from satisfactory.

Agarwal, Dr. Himanshu (26-27 November, 2005) in his paper "Impediments to FDI Inflow in India" presented at UGC sponsored National Seminar at S D (PG) College, Muzaffarnagar mentioned that it is increasingly common for governments to offer incentives to foreign firms to invest in their countries. Such incentives take many forms, but the most common are tax concessions, low – interest loans, and grants or subsidies. Incentives are motivated by a desire to gain from the resource – transfer and employment effects of FDI. They are also motivated by a desire to capture FDI away from other potential host countries. Host governments use a wide range of controls to restrict FDI in one way or another. The two most common are: (i) ownership restraints and (ii) performance requirements.

Nayak D.N. (2004) in his paper "Canadian Foreign Direct Investment in India: Some Observations", analyse the patterns and trends of Canadian FDI in India. He finds out that India does not figure very much in the investment plans of Canadian firms. The reasons for the same is the indifferent attitude of Canadians towards India and lack of information of investment opportunities in India are the important contributing factor for such an unhealthy trends in economic relation between India and Canada. He suggested some measures such as publishing of regular documents like newsletter that would highlight opportunities in India and a detailed focus on India's area of strength so that Canadian firms could come forward and discuss their areas of expertise would got long way in enhancing Canadian FDI in India.

Naga Raj R. (2003) in his article "Foreign Direct Investment in India in the 1990s: Trends and Issues" discusses the trends in FDI in India in the 1990s and compare them with China. The study raises some issues on the effects of the recent investments on the domestic economy. Based on the analytical discussion and comparative experience, the study concludes by suggesting a realistic foreign investment policy.

Gazioglou S. and Mc Causland W.D. (2000) in their study "An International Economic Analysis of FDI and International Indebtedness" developed a micro –foundations framework of analysis of FDI and integrated it into a macro level analysis. They highlighted the importance of profit repatriation in generating different effects of FDI on net international debt, trade and real exchange rate in developed economies compared to less developed economies.

Bhagwati J.N. (1978) in his study "Anatomy and Consequences of Exchange Control Regimes" analyzed the impact of FDI on international trade. He concluded that countries actively pursuing export led growth strategy can reap enormous benefits from FDI.

5. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Policy in India

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is now recognized as an important engine of economic development. FDI flow as external finance is being preferred in the Asian region because they are non-debt creating, non-volatile and their returns depend on the performance of the projects financed by the investors. In the current global scenario, increasing competition, rapid technological change and other challenging economic handicaps is becoming the chief contributor to the inflow of FDI in most developing countries. In a nation like India, the complimentary and catalytic role of FDI is highly valuable. The reasons for this approach can be enlisted as under:

1. India does not have sufficient reservoirs of domestic capital inflows required for economic growth and industrialisation. Therefore, it is necessary to invite foreign capital.
2. Additional resources flows, such as transfer of technology and provision of training, often accompany FDI capital flows.
3. Domestic entrepreneurs may be hesitant to invest into certain lines of production due to lack of experience. In such a situation FDI is proved to be as an antibiotic.
4. The need for foreign investment arises in the early stages of development when capital market is not developed in the country. Hence, foreign investment is essential to make a repo between the demand and the supply.

Foreign Investment in India is governed by the FDI policy announced by the Government of India and the provision of the Foreign Exchange Management Act (FEMA) 1999. The Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India is the nodal agency for reviewing the FDI policy on continued basis and changes in sectoral policy/ sectoral equity capital. The FDI policy is notified through Press Notes by the Secretariat for Industrial Assistance (SIA), Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP). The foreign investors are free to invest in India, except few sectors/ activities, where prior approval from the RBI or Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB) would be required. With the growing integration of the Indian economy with global markets, there has been a rapid transformation of the Indian retailing sector as reflected in the growth of organized retailing. Indian retailing sector is witnessing increasing investments from the corporate sector, development of various retail formats and shopping infrastructure. Foreign Direct Investment has flowed in to different sectors associated with retailing such as wholesale cash-and-carry, franchising, local manufacturing, etc. This is evident from the fact that India is emerging rapidly as a sourcing hub for international retailers. The industrial policy of 1965, allowed MNCs to venture through technical collaboration in India. However, the country faced two severe crises in the form of foreign exchange and financial resource mobilization during the second five year plan (1956-61). Therefore, the government adopted a liberal attitude by allowing more frequent equity participation to foreign enterprises, and to accept equity capital in technical collaborations. The government also provides many incentives such as tax concessions, simplification of licensing procedures and de-reserving some industries such as drugs, aluminium, heavy electrical equipments, fertilizers, etc in order to further boost the FDI inflows in the country. The government introduces reforms in the industrial sector, aimed at increasing competency, efficiency and growth in industry through a stable, pragmatic and non-discriminatory policy for FDI flow. Infact, in the early nineties, Indian economy faced severe Balance of payment crisis. Exports began to experience serious difficulties. There was a marked increase in petroleum prices because of the gulf war. The crippling external debts were debilitating the economy. India was left with that much amount of foreign exchange reserves which can finance its three weeks of imports. The out flowing of foreign currency which was deposited by the Indian NRI's gave a further jolt to Indian economy. The overall Balance of Payment reached at Rs. (-) 4471 crores. Inflation reached at its highest level of 13 per cent. Foreign reserves of the country stood at Rs.11416 crores. The continued political uncertainty in the country during this period adds further to worsen the situation. As a result, India's credit rating fell in the international market for both short- term and long term borrowing. All these developments put the economy at that time on the verge of default in respect of external payments liability. In this critical face of Indian economy the then finance Minister of India Dr. Manmohan Singh with the help of World Bank and IMF introduced the macro – economic stabilization and structural adjustment programme.

As it seems in the present economic scape, a developing country that higher rate of growth and fast economic development can only be achieved through inviting FDI. And, it is worth quoting here when a communist country like China can adopt the policy of inviting foreign capital for its rapid development, why should we not.

As a result of these reforms, India opened its door to FDI inflows and adopted a more liberal foreign policy in order to restore the confidence of foreign investors. India also became the member of MIGA (Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency) for protection of foreign investments.

6. Status of FDI and Growth of Retail Sector in India

Foreign direct investment is a mirror that reflects the extent to which a country and its companies have integrated globally. Therefore, China, in terms of attracting FDI, has set standards for India. In 2004, this was \$54 billion for China while India attracted only \$1. The situation turns into more pitiful pictorial ratio if Hong Kong is added as de facto part of China i.e., 1:15. FDI inflows are not only being invited for money. It is also about inflow of technology, modern manufacturing practices and access to global markets. It is the foreign technology that has transformed an unknown Chinese textile firm into a major supplier to Wal-Mart and J.C.Penney, while top notch Indian companies like Raymonds and Arvind are struggling even today to become a part of this global supply chain.

Moreover, consumer electronics (Haier and TCL), automobiles (Shanghai Motor Company and Nanjing Motors) and computers and high-tech (Lenovo and Ben-Q) are just some examples of how Chinese companies have leveraged foreign investments to emerge as global players. Even in India, the two sectors - IT and ITES - that have attracted the most FDI are the ones that are the most global with global companies.

In India, Foreign Direct Investment is allowed in franchising (unless specifically prohibited) and commission agent's services. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) can be a powerful catalyst to spur competition in the retail industry, due to the current scenario of low competition and poor productivity. As per the current policy, a foreign player can enter the Indian distribution services sectors under the following conditions, "Trading is permitted under automatic route with Foreign Direct Investment up to 51 per cent provided it is primarily export activity, and the undertaking is an export house/ trading house/ super trading house/star trading house."

The following table shows the latest figures of FDI. The highest FDI inflow to India was in the year 2008 amounting to US\$ 43.41 billion.

Table 3: FDI Inflow to India

Year	FDI Inflow US \$ Billion (approximated to two digits after decimal)
2000	3.58
2001	5.47
2002	5.62
2003	4.32
2004	5.77
2005	7.27
2006	20.03
2007	25.23
2008	43.41
2009	35.58
2010	27.40
2011	36.49
2012	23.99

Source: World Bank Database

FDI in Single- Brand Retail

Up to 100 per cent FDI is permissible in single-brand retail conditions stipulate that:

- I) Only single-brand products are sold;
- II) Products are sold under the same brand internationally;
- III) Single-brand products include only those identified during manufacturing;
- IV) Any additional product categories to be sold under single-brand retail must first receive additional government approval.

FDI in single-brand implies that a retail store with foreign investment can only sell one brand.

FDI in Multi-Brand Retail

FDI in multi brand retail generally refers to selling multiple brands under one roof. Currently, this sector is limited to a maximum of 49 per cent foreign equity participation.

In July, 2010, the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP) and the Ministry of Commerce circulated a discussion paper on allowing FDI in multi-brand retail. The committee of secretaries, led by Cabinet Secretary Ajit Seth, recommended opening the retail sector for FDI with a 51 per cent capital reinvestment into backend operations. Notably, the paper does not put forward any upper limit on FDI in multi brand retail.

The long-awaited scheme has been sent to the Cabinet for approval, but no decision has yet been made. There appears to be a broad consensus within the Committee of Secretaries that a 51 per cent cap on FDI in multi – brand retail is acceptable. Meanwhile the Department of Consumer Affairs has supported the case for a 49 per cent cap and the Small and Medium Enterprises Ministry has said the Government should limit FDI in multi – brand retail to 18 per cent. In terms of location, the proposed scheme allows investment in towns with populations of at least 10 lakh (1 million), while retailers with large space requirements may also be allowed to open shop within a 10 kilometer radius of such cities.

Table 4: Multi Brand Retail FDI Policy in Other Countries

Country	FDI Limit
China	100 per cent
Thailand	100 per cent
Russia	100 per cent
Indonesia	100 per cent

Source: Technopak

The 51% foreign direct investment in multi-brand retail is likely to include foreign portfolio investment as well, as the government is keen to ensure that the restriction on foreign ownership is not breached.

The government is wary that any breach in the limit will give more fodder to those opposed to opening of the sector to foreign investors, a hard fought reform for the UPA government that lost some key allies on the issue. The composite cap could restrict the options of existing listed multi-brand retailers that may be keen to sell stake to multinational stores.

Under the current rules, investment by foreign institutional investors can go up to 24% in a listed company and can be further raised with a shareholder resolution to up to the sectoral limit cap. This implies that a listed multi-brand retail player that has FDI could have foreign ownership much more than 51% cap as stipulated in the policy, a situation the government is keen to avoid.

Sectors such as telecom, banking, information and broadcasting also have composite caps wherein the cap is applicable on all forms of foreign investment and not just FDI. The policy on multi-brand retail mentions 51% cap on FDI but the view across the stakeholder ministries is that the intent was to allow foreign investment upto that limit. The government is concerned about the sensitivities attached to the sector and wants to tread with caution.

Why a Composite Cap?

- Under the current rules, investment by FIIs can go up to 24% in a listed company and can be further raised with a shareholder resolution to up to the sectoral limit cap
- This means a listed multi-brand retail player that has FDI could have foreign ownership much more than 51% cap as stipulated in the policy

A composite FDI-FII cap will ensure the 51% limit is not breached

SECTORS SUCH AS TELECOM, BANKING, INFORMATION AND BROADCASTING ALSO HAVE COMPOSITE CAPS

What are its implications?

It will restrict the options of existing listed multi-brand retailers that may be keen to sell stake to MNC retailers

Only 11 states have allowed FDI in the sector. However, foreign institutional investors (FIIs) investors will not face the sector conditions imposed on foreign retailers that invest in India. Foreign retailers that want to set up retail stores in India have to mandatorily invest at least 50% of the total FDI brought in has to be invested in 'backend infrastructure' within three years of the first tranche of FDI wherein back-end infrastructure includes capital expenditure on agriculture market produce infrastructure and others. At least \$100 million FDI has to be brought in by the foreign investors.

Foreign retailers also have to adhere to minimum sourcing requirement from small and medium enterprises. Moreover, any entity with FDI can only set up shop only in those states that have allowed FDI in retail. India had opened the sector in September 2012 but is yet to see any FDI in the sector.

However, under the FIPB route- 100 percent Foreign Direct Investment is permitted in case of trading companies for the following activities:

- Exports,
- Bulk imports with ex-port/ ex-bonded warehouse sales,
- Cash-and-carry wholesale trading,
- Other import of goods or services provided at least 75 percent is for procurement and sale of goods and services among the companies of the same group and not for third party use or onward transfer/ distribution/sales.

The following kinds of trading are also permitted, subject to provisions of EXIM Policy:

- Companies for providing after sales services (that is not trading per se).
- Domestic trading of products of joint ventures is permitted at the wholesale level for such trading companies who wish to market manufactured products on behalf of their joint ventures in which they have equity participation in India.
- Trading of hi-tech items/items requiring specialized after sales service.
- Trading of items for social sector.
- Trading of hi-tech, medical and diagnostic items.
- Trading of items sourced from the small scale sector under which, based on technology provided and laid down quality specifications, a company can market that item under its brand name.
- Domestic sourcing of products for exports.
- Test marketing of such items for which a company has approval for manufacture provided such test marketing facility will be for a period of two years, and investment in setting up facilities commences simultaneously with test marketing.

7. Causes and Reasons for Low FDI in India

In this section, some of the weakness and constraints on achieving higher FDI inflows into India are closely lighted upon. Some factors may be more relevant for first time investors with no previous experience of investment in India. The review presents broad generalizations basing on past experiences.

a) Attitudinal Assessment: Although, economic reforms introduced in nineties have paved the path to foreign capital but, some unhappy episodes in the past have given multiple effects adversely to the business environment in India. There has been a perception abroad that foreign investors are looked at with some suspicion even today in India. When a foreign investor considers making any new investment decision, it goes through four stages in the decision making process and action cycle, namely, (a) screening, (b)planning, (e) implementing and (d) operating and expanding. Often India is dropped out at the screening stage itself. This is primarily because our promotional attitude is quite often of a general nature and not corporate specific. India is, moreover, a multi-cultural society and a large number of multinational companies (MNC) do not understand the diversity and the multi-plural nature of the society and the different stakeholders in this country.

All investments, foreign and domestic are made under the expectation of future profits. The economy benefits if economic policy fosters competition, creates a well functioning modern regulatory system and discourages artificial monopolies created by the government through entry barriers. A recognition and understanding of these facts can result in a more positive attitude towards FDI.

b) Policy Frameworks: Most of the problems for investors arise because of domestic policy, rules and procedures and not the FDI policy per se or its rules and procedures. The FDI policy, which has a lot of

positive features, is discussed, before highlighting the domestic policy related difficulties that are commonly the focus of adverse comment by investors and intermediaries.

c) Quality Of Infrastructure: Poor infrastructure affects the productivity of the economy as a whole and particular to GDP/per capita GDP. It also reduces the comparative advantage of industries that are more intensive in the use of such infrastructure. In the context of FDI, poor infrastructure has a greater effect on export production than on production for the domestic market. FDI directed at the domestic market suffers the same handicap and additional costs as domestic manufacturers that are competing for the domestic market. Inadequate and poor quality roads, railways and ports, however raise export costs vis-à-vis global competitors having better quality and lower cost infrastructure. These costs have been quantified by the CII- World Bank study of Investment environment in India and its comparison with similar World Bank studied on China and other countries. As a foreign direct investor planning to set up an export base in developing/ emerging economies has the option of choosing between India and other locations with better infrastructure, India is handicapped in attracting export oriented FDI.

Poor infrastructure is found to be the most important constraint for construction and engineering industries. It is also evident by the survey made by Mckinsey, "Law, rules, regulations relating to infrastructure are sometimes missing or unclear e.g. LNG and the power sector is beset with multiple problems such as State monopoly, bankruptcy and weak regulators".

d) State Obstacles: Taxes levied on transportation of goods from State to State (such as octroi and entry tax) adversely impact the economic environment for export production. Such taxes impose both cost and time delays on movement of inputs used in production of export products as well as in transport of the latter to the ports. Mckinsey has put this fact in its research that, "Differential sale and excise taxes (States and Centre) on small and large companies are found to be a deterrent to FDI in sectors such as textiles". Investments that could raise the productivity and quality of textiles and thus make them competitive in global markets remain unprofitable because they cannot overcome the tax advantage given to small producers in the domestic market. As this is a State subject, the States have to take the lead in simplifying and modernising the policy and rules relating to this sector. At the local level (sub-state) issues pertaining to land acquisition, land use change, power connection, building plan approval are sources of project implementation delay. The State level issues are also being considered by the Govindarajan committee with a view to seeing how they can be alleviated.

e) Legal Delays: Though India's Anglo Saxon legal system as codified is considered by many legal experts to be superior to that of many other emerging economies. It is often found in practice to be an obstacle to investment. One of the reasons is the inordinate delay that are the interlocutory procedures that characterise judicial procedures. As a result the "Rule of law," which has often been cited as one of the attractive features of the Indian economy for foreign investors, is found to be a significant positive factor by only 3 per cent for FDI in India.

8. Benefits of FDI in Retail Sector

Benefits include moving away from an industry focus on intermediaries and job creation.

a) Infusion of Capital: As discussed above, retailing depends on supply chain logistics. An efficient logistics - based on well-developed networks of transportation, communication, and storage infrastructure – not only provides timely and uninterrupted market access to the producers but also ensures quality and lower prices to the consumers. For example, without the development of appropriate storage infrastructure, the farmers cannot have an access to an efficient market system that pays fair prices and have to fall prey to unscrupulous middlemen. These middlemen pay lower prices to the farmers and charge higher prices to the retailers. Furthermore, since a significant portion of the produces are destroyed in the process of being transported from the farmers to the retailers and ultimately to the consumers, the consumers have to pay higher prices for relatively low quality products. In India, primarily due to the unorganised and fragmented nature of the retail sector, there is a severe shortage of funds for investment in the basic infrastructure required mainly for back-end retail logistics. The retailers are too small to make such large investments. Although government has stepped in, the infrastructure built by the government has not been adequate.

Allowing FDI in retailing is expected to go a long way in alleviating this situation because the large retailers would build the necessary infrastructure to create an integrated back-end supply chain for efficiency.

b) Technology Transfer: In addition to augmenting physical capital stock, FDI in developing countries also acts as a conduit of technology transfer. Foreign capital brings along advanced technology from developed countries that increases productivity. In retailing, advanced technologies will tremendously improve processing, grading, handling and packaging of goods. The use of cold-storage facilities, refrigerated vans, pre-cooling chambers will reduce wastage and help maintain product quality. Electronic weighing, billing, and barcode scanning will add to accuracy and efficiency. These efficiency gains will lower price and improve quality for the consumers.

c) Moving away from intermediary-only benefits: Today's intermediaries amid producers and customers add no value to the products, adding hugely to final costs instead. By the time products filter through various intermediaries and into the marketplace, they lose freshness and quality, and often go to waste. However, intermediaries garner huge profits by distributing these losses between producers and customers by buying products at low prices from producers, but selling at extremely marked-up prices to consumers. In an unbalanced system that incorporates multiple intermediaries simply for logistics, only intermediaries benefit. With organized retail, every intermediate step – procurement, processing, transport and delivery – adds value to the product. This happens because it uses international best practices and modern technology, ensuring maximum efficiency and minimum waste. Organized retail enables on-site processing, scientific handling and quick transport through cold storage chains to the final consumer.

Once modern retailers introduce an organized model, other vendors, including small retailers, would mechanically copy this model to improve efficiencies, boost margins and stay in business. Organized retail would thereby bring more stability to prices, unlike the present system where hoarding and artificial shortages by profiteering intermediaries push up product prices.

d) Job Creation: Despite predictions from some analysts that millions of jobs would be lost due to FDI in retail, it may in fact be the other way around. With the entry of branded retailers, the market will increase, creating additional employment in retail and other tertiary sectors. Given their professional approach, organized retailers will allot some quantity of resources towards the training and development of the resources they employ.

9. Impact of FDI in Retail on the Indian Economy

Indian Economy is a developing economy. We have the same problems as a developing economy has. But, on the contrary, we have also a multi-face population too. The issue is not simply of Foreign invasion in India or not. Nehru ever opposed foreign introduction in business. He was somewhat afraid of Imperialism, which had its own issues and after-math. But, on the contrary, in my opinion the issue lies in the well being of the mass. The issue lies in the *roti, kapda aur makaan* to the last one in the country. Bibek Debroy, Professor, Centre for Policy Research writes in his article "Twists in Indian Retail Tale" (ET 2.12.11) that *"...as a shade of grey, the present decision is no more than the thin edge of liberalization. All liberalisation is good for consumers. The colour of competition (national versus foreign) doesn't matter. There is choice, better quality and better service. There is down ward pressure on prices. Post-1991, this elementary proposition of economics has been empirically vindicated whenever competition has been allowed to seep in. There is no reason for consumers to be exploited by the Future Group, Shoppers Stop or Vishal Retail. However, getting organized retail to work takes years and years. China is the obvious example, where organized retail penetration is still less than 10 per cent. Kirana stores have resilience. They change their line of business. They adapt. One should have faith in that resilience."*

The IMF definition of FDI includes as many as twelve different elements – equity capital, reinvested earnings of foreign companies, inter company debt transactions, short –term and long – term loans, financial leasing, trade credits, grants, bonds, non-cash acquisition of equity, investment made by foreign venture capital investors, earnings data of indirectly-held FDI enterprises, control premium and non-competition fee. India, However, does not adopt any other element other than equity capital reported on the basis of issue or transfer of equity or preference shares to foreign direct investors. Figure explores the process how FDI is

important in utilizing of our economic resources and generating the employment in country as well as important for creating economic prosperity.

Fig.3: Impact of FDI on Indian Economy

Moreover, Paradigm shift from farmer to consumer, the influx of foreign funds into multi-brand retail

Fig. 2: Impact on Various Sectors of Indian Economy

<p>FARMERS</p> <p>TODAY Vegetables pass through five intermediaries: aggregator, market trader, wholesaler, sub-wholesaler and retailer. Each adds to the price.</p> <p>TOMORROW The large retailer can buy directly from the farmer, offering much higher price. Only one intermediary – the aggregator – will be needed.</p>		
<p>IMPORTERS</p> <p>TODAY Malls may have sprung up across India, but they are still very small compared to the mega stores in many countries across the world.</p> <p>TOMORROW FDI would bring more capital, enable setting up of large stores and offer jobs to millions besides pump priming the sluggish realty sector.</p>		
<p>KIRANA STORES</p> <p>TODAY Consumers have a choice of shopping at malls peppered across their towns and cities or in the kirana stores in their neighbourhoods.</p> <p>TOMORROW The choice gets bigger. Giant megastores will sell labelled items like stationery, footwear, clothes etc at deep discounts.</p>		

will change the rules of the game for all players. A look at how the scenario will change is presented through this image:

10. CONCLUSION

Prime Minister Manmohan Singh while commenting upon the people's rage against FDI in Retail says, "We have thought a lot and firmly believe that this decision will benefit us a lot... this will help to bring latest technology to the agriculture sector, less wastage and more jobs." The policy must come with riders to umbrella protect the neighborhood stores, farmers and small and medium-sized enterprises. If effectively implemented, such FDI has the potential to:

- It may bring not only foreign capital but also technology and expertise.
- It may help to build an efficient linkage between the back – end supply chain and the front – end via capital investment and technological inputs.

- c. It can develop a better farmer to consumer network through better expertise and control and bulk purchases from the farmers.
- d. It may ensure efficient and effective transportation by reducing transit costs and other relative costs.
- e. Foreign companies have better managerial capacities in minimizing the wastage through effective cold storage, transport infrastructure, warehousing, treatment, processing and perishing.
- f. It may help farmers (the client) in providing them consultancy about increasing productive and preserving the harvest.
- g. It may put more options of price, quality and quantity against the consumer in different forms and applications. Through which consumer can feel comfortable with the product.
- h. It helps to generate employment in Medium and small size industries, farm and the stores itself for the Indian youth.

This way, the objectives are fulfilled and the hypothesis taken in the beginning of the research paper is proved fully as following:

- a) Foreign Direct Investment has a positive impact on retail sector in India because there are low capital formation, lack of technological innovation in the country, high rise of middle class population and an urge for high western level living.
- b) With the advent of computer-oriented jobs, increase in super-speciality education and establishment of new generation tarde-systems, the income level has changed drastically in the middle class in India.
- c) The growth of retail sector has contributed directly to the growth of Indian Economic Development in terms of capital outlay, employment and technology infusion.
- d) Organised Retail Industry has created drastic opportunities for every type of job-seekers in the country.

Thus, Political influence must leave their old outlook as overpowered by the Imperialism and government should foresee the future and rising demands of the country. Modern youth needs a respectable and comfortable job, quality education, rural areas need upbringing and urban areas need industrialization.

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